

Improving The Oral Reading and Comprehension Skills of the High School Students Through Phonological-Based Intervention

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ABSTRACT

The Philippines consistently performs poorly in reading comprehension on international assessments, underscoring the pressing need to confront reading challenges experienced by struggling readers. In response to this imperative, the Kabataan Kakikitaan ng Katatasan sa Pagbasa (K3P) Program was launched through a collaborative effort between the Department of Education and San Isidro College in Malaybalay Bukidnon, aimed at innovatively addressing these challenges through utilizing Phonological-Based Intervention. The study involved twenty struggling readers from Casisang National High School during the school year 2022-23, selected through purposive sampling (total population sampling) for participation in the intervention program and focus group discussions. Employing a concurrent mixed-method research approach, the study utilized quantitative measures, including pre-and post-tests using PHIL-IRI, to evaluate progress in reading and comprehension skills, complemented by qualitative insights from focus group discussions to capture participant experiences. The results of the 10-week intervention initiative indicated a notable enhancement in both oral reading and comprehension skills among the participants. This favorable outcome highlighted the effectiveness of the intervention in improving the literacy capabilities of those involved. The challenges faced by participants, such as feeling overwhelmed by household tasks, lacking family support, and experiencing bullying, underscored the diverse difficulties they confront as struggling readers. Engagement in a comprehensive literacy intervention program has proven instrumental in enhancing students' reading skills. Consequently, the findings highlight the importance of persisting with Phonological-based

Instruction in teaching and the necessity for comprehensive support mechanisms to improve students' reading skills.

Subject Area

Oral Reading and Comprehension

Keywords: *Intervention Program; Kabataan Kakikitaan ng Katatasan sa Pagbasa (K3P) Program; Struggling Readers*

INTRODUCTION

Embarking on the journey into a world rich with books and knowledge, a child's acquisition of reading skills becomes a pivotal cornerstone in life, unlocking a wealth of information and essential insights for navigating future experiences (Kaya, 2015). However, the Philippines needs help with reading proficiency, with reports indicating subpar performance in comprehension, science, and mathematics exams. A World Bank study reveals that 90% of Filipino children encounter difficulties in reading, impacting academic achievement, lifelong learning, and the country's global competitiveness. Addressing this issue requires initiatives and innovation, such as improving reading programs, allocating resources for literacy support, and fostering a widespread culture of reading to enhance educational outcomes and bolster the nation's competitive standing (Tomas et al., 2021).

In response to this urgent need, the Kabataan Kakikitaan ng Katatasan sa Pagbasa (K3P) Program was an initiative launched collaboratively by the Department of Education and San Isidro College in Malaybalay, Bukidnon, aimed to address literacy challenges through a Phonological-Based Intervention. The initiative introduces phonological awareness as a fundamental framework. Through a meticulously structured approach, students engage in activities such as phonetic awareness, blending words, and targeted drills strategically designed to nurture and enhance the reading skills of those still mastering the intricacies of reading, providing a robust foundation for literacy.

Phonological awareness (PA), described as the capacity to manipulate the phonological components of words, is integral to a child's cognitive, verbal, and emotional processes. According to Johnson (2023), PA is deemed essential for learning to read as it empowers individuals to recognize and manipulate the sounds within words. Extensive research by Veríssimo et al. (2021), Hogan et al. (2005), and Milankov et al. (2021) underscores the critical need for early phonological awareness stimulation in enhancing overall reading abilities. Despite this consensus, a notable research gap exists in implementing intentional strategies, particularly in the underutilized realm of phonemic awareness.

In response to these gaps, the program implemented Phonological-Based Instruction to address reading difficulties among high school students. The program aligned with the teaching and learning theme, focusing on students grappling with learning to read and the application of phonics by teachers. The program's dual goals aimed to equip future educators with a profound understanding of Phonics and Phonological Awareness, emphasizing discrete, methodical instruction of letters and combinations to enhance blending into simple words, fostering increased

student understanding and confidence. Simultaneously, the intervention targets identified struggling junior high school students, adopting a comprehensive approach to literacy development. This initiative sought to bridge existing research gaps and contribute valuable insights to effectively implementing phonological-based strategies for improved reading skills.

THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study assumed that utilizing Phonological-based Instruction in Teaching helps address the reading problems of struggling high school students identified as frustration level. Schema Theory supports this assumption.

According to Ngabut (2015), schema and related notions emerged from cognitive science research that discovered the role of background knowledge in language comprehension. Pankin (2021) has defined Schema Theory as a subfield of cognitive science that studies how the brain structures knowledge. A schema is a logically structured set of knowledge about a topic or event. Based on prior experience, it is consulted to aid current comprehension or action. Pankin's comprehension and that this schema is individualized. Hence, the meaning of the degree of meaning is determined by the reader. Navarrete (2019) proposed three types of schemata that a reader mainly utilizes. These are script knowledge, knowledge of text structure, and language knowledge.

Comprehending a text, based on this theory and according to this approach, is an interactive process between the reader's background knowledge and the text. Therefore, the ability to relate the textual materials to one's own knowledge is required for effective comprehension. Understanding words, phrases, and entire texts need more than just language understanding, according to Ngabut (2015).

Phonological awareness, also known as sound awareness, involves knowledge of how to produce sounds and how they come together to make words. Children need to know how sounds work before learning to read print materials. They must understand that words are made up of speech sounds or phonemes. It is an essential literacy skill that the inability can often lead to reading and writing difficulties.

Researchers have determined that this distinct relationship between phonological awareness and reading success lasts throughout the school. It goes without saying that any Filipino child with adequate reading abilities has a better chance of succeeding in school than a child with low reading skills, and those with weak reading skills are more often than not diagnosed with reading impairment when properly tested. Poor reading ability manifests itself in various ways, including poor comprehension and incorrect pronunciation. If adequate assistance is not provided early on, the child's intellectual, social, and psychological development may be harmed.

Facun-Granadozo (2014) acknowledged that understanding phonemic awareness and phonics enhanced the teachers' preparedness to teach concepts in reading. They further said that engaging in reflective thinking while working for mastery of these concepts deepened their awareness of unpreparedness and reconnected them to their goal of being effective teachers in delivering quality literacy instruction.

Consequently, this present undertaking focuses on the use of phonological-based instruction to improve the reading proficiency of junior high school students. This study endeavors to narrow the gap in the reading deficits of struggling high school students.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Phonological –based instruction to improve the reading proficiency of junior high school students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the participants' oral reading skills level before and after the Phonological –based instruction in terms of:
 - 1.1 oral reading; and
 - 1.2 comprehension?
2. Is there a significant difference in the reading scores of the participants before and after the Phonological –based instruction interventions?
3. What factors contribute to the challenges faced by participants in developing their reading skills?

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study employed a concurrent nested mixed methods research design. According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2011), this research design involves integrating quantitative and qualitative data into a conventional study methodology. Both quantitative and qualitative data will be used in this investigation. The quantitative part uncovered the implications of utilizing Phonological –based instruction among the struggling junior high school students in improving their oral and comprehension English reading skills, while the qualitative part determined the participants' identified factors affecting their oral reading deficiency.

Through the quantitative method, students' oral reading performance was tabulated for frequencies, percentages and mean distribution. It was gathered in determining the effectiveness of the Phonological –based instruction contributing to the oral skills proficiency of the students, while the qualitative part determined the causes or factors contributing to their reading deficit, hence, the use of concurrent nested mixed methods research design is deemed appropriate for the study.

Furthermore, the participants in this study that were selected from the first phase in the quantitative part were a subset of the participants selected in the other phase as in nested. Thus, both data were then collected concurrently.

PARTICIPANTS OF THE STUDY AND SAMPLING

The participants of the study were the struggling high school students of Casisang National High School identified as the frustration level in reading. Through purposive sampling, the participants of the study are the twenty (20) Grade 8, 9 and 10 Junior High School students. The students are enrolled in Casisang National High School, city of Malaybalay, province of Bukidnon for Academic Year 2022-2023.

The Phil-IRI Oral Reading Test, an individualized reading assessment instrument of Department of Education for recording each student's performance was used to gather the data. The instrument was used to identify the student's oral reading errors noting how many words a student reads each minute; and assessed a student's comprehension of the passage that was read.

DATA GATHERING PROCEDURE

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher and the dean of the School of Education signed the Memorandum of Agreement with the principal of the Junior high school in Casisang National High School in the city of Malaybalay. After the MOA signing, Phil-IRI Oral Reading Test was administered to the participants. During the MOA signing, the principal explained to the parents and participants the intent of the Kabataan Kakikitaan ng Katatasan sa Pagbasa (K3P) Initiative. The following protocols in administering the Phil-IRI Oral Reading Test were observed. First, the students were assured that the test and the activities would not affect their grades in the subject. They were also reminded of the purpose of the test and the importance of genuine efforts and honesty to ensure the validity of the test. Second, they were asked to sign the Informed Consent Form to confirm that they agreed to take part in the study and that they understood their voluntary participation in the study.

To obtain an extensive understanding of the data descriptive statistics such as percentage and frequency distribution were used in order to determine the participants' level of oral reading skills; for problem number 2, the inferential statistics (T-test) for paired samples was used to compare their reading level skills before and after interventions. For problem 3, Thematic analysis was used to determine on the challenges experienced by the participants for having oral reading deficit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analyses and interpretations of data obtained from the study participants are presented in this section. Presentation is organized in accordance with the list of problems set out in the problem statement.

Participants' Reading Skills Level Before and After Interventions Utilizing Phonological – Based Instruction in Oral Reading and Comprehension

Table 1 presents the percentage and frequency distribution of oral reading skill levels before and after interventions employing Phonological techniques. Initially, all twenty participants exhibited a *frustration level* in oral reading, constituting 100% during the pre-test, conducted before the intervention. A detailed examination of the data reveals that twelve students (60%) were initially assessed at the frustration level, while eight students (40%) demonstrated significant improvement, transitioning from the *frustration level* to the *instructional level* after participating in the intervention program. This suggests that the Phonological interventions had a positive impact on enhancing oral reading skills, as reflected in the observed shift from frustration to instructional levels among the participating students.

Table 1.

Frequency distribution of oral reading skills level before and after interventions utilizing Phonological Awareness

	Oral Reading	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
		F	%	F	%
Independent	97-100%	0	0	0	0
Instructional	90-96%	0	0	8	40
Frustration	89% and below	20	100	12	60
TOTAL		20	100	20	100

The transition of twelve students from the frustration level to the instructional level signifies a substantial improvement in their oral reading skills. This improvement implies that the Phonological techniques employed in the intervention program were effective in addressing the challenges and fostering progress in oral reading proficiency. It implies that these techniques have the potential to be valuable tools for educators and practitioners seeking to enhance students' reading proficiency. However, it also indicates the need for further research to understand the factors contributing to the varying responses to the intervention, as 40% of the participants showed improvement while 60% remained at the *frustration level* after the intervention. The existence of varying responses among participants, with majority remaining at the *frustration level*, highlights the complexity of addressing oral reading challenges. This variation highlights the need for additional investigation to explore the variables influencing the disparate results. It is possible to improve intervention strategies to make them more focused and individualized by having a better understanding of the reasons behind some participants' positive responses and others' negative ones.

The findings that phonological approaches can be useful in enhancing oral reading abilities is supported by numerous studies. For instance, a study by Bratsch-Hines et al. (2021) and Jiménez-Fernández et al. (2022) discovered that spelling, comprehension, and reading fluency and accuracy were all improved by the phonological intervention.

Table 2.

Percentage and Frequency Distribution of Students' Comprehension Skills Level before and after Interventions utilizing Phonological Awareness

	Comprehension Score	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
		F	%	F	%
Independent	80-100%	0	0	2	10
Instructional	59-79%	1	5	9	45
Frustration	58% and below	19	95	9	45
TOTAL		20	100	20	100

Table 2 presents the percentage and frequency distribution of students' comprehension skills before and after interventions employing Phonological Awareness. It is evident that prior to the intervention, 95% or 19 participants were at the *frustration level*, while only 5% or 1 participant was at the *instructional level*. Following the intervention, noteworthy progress was observed among junior high school students, with 10% or 2 students achieving the independent level and 45% or 9 students attaining the *instructional level* in reading comprehension.

The results suggest that the intervention improved junior high school students' reading comprehension skills because fewer students expressed *frustration* and a significant proportion of students attained higher proficiency levels. This implies that the applied intervention was successful in addressing and enhancing the participants' comprehension difficulties. These findings are consistent with Pfof et al. (2019) and Bratsch-Hines et al. (2019) studies that have shown that Phonological Awareness techniques can be effective in improving reading skills and fostering progress in oral reading proficiency.

Significant Difference in the Reading Scores of the Participants Before and After the Interventions

Table 3 shows the mean of oral reading was 3.00 (SD=.00) before intervention and 2.60 (SD=.50) after intervention. The difference between the mean level of oral reading before and after the intervention was examined with a paired samples t-test. Oral reading was significantly higher after the interventions than before it $t(19)=3.59, p = .002$.

Table 3.

Significant difference in the reading scores of the participants before and after the interventions

Reading skill level before and after intervention		Mean	Std. Dev.	N	t	df	p	Decision
Oral Reading	Pre-test	3.00	0.00	20	3.59	19	0.002	There is a significant difference
	Post-test	2.60	0.50	20				
Comprehension	Pre-test	2.95	0.22	20	3.59	19	0.002	There is a significant difference
	Post-test	2.35	0.67	20				

The given statistical results indicate the mean level of comprehension before and after an intervention, along with their standard deviations. A paired sample t-test was performed to examine the difference in mean comprehension scores before and after the intervention. Results showed that comprehension scores were significantly higher after the intervention than before, $t(19) = 3.59, p = .002$. A paired sample t-test is a statistical method that compares the means of two measurements taken from the same individuals or related units. It determines whether there is statistical evidence that the mean difference between paired observations is significantly different from zero. In this case, a test was used to evaluate the effect of the intervention on comprehension results

The obtained t-value of 3.59 indicates the magnitude of the difference between the mean comprehension scores before and after the intervention, while the p-value of .002 suggests that this difference is statistically significant. A p-value of .002 means that if there were no true difference in comprehension scores before and after the intervention, the probability of observing a difference as large as the one obtained is .002, which is less than the conventional threshold of .05. Therefore, the results provide strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis that there is no difference in comprehension scores before and after the intervention.

Overall, the interpretation of the statistical results presented indicates that the intervention using Phonological awareness significantly improved comprehension scores, as evidenced by a

higher mean comprehension score post-intervention and statistically significant one-sample t-test results.

Similar finding was found by Bratsch-Hines et al. (2019) indicating that students with speech or language impairment who received early phonological awareness interventions improved their reading comprehension. Sucena et al. (2022) reported significant improvements in reading and comprehension among Emirati students with learning disabilities due to repeated reading intervention. Dudyh (2015) underscores the significance of teaching phonological awareness as a valuable intervention for supporting struggling readers. These studies provide evidence that phonological awareness interventions can significantly improve reading comprehension skills.

Factors Affecting Their Reading Difficulty

Themes

1. *feeling overwhelmed by household tasks*
2. *lacking family support*
3. *experiencing bullying*

Feeling Overwhelmed by Household Tasks

Participants shared insights into the challenges they face in reading, attributing one key factor to their domestic responsibilities. They articulated that their reading difficulties stem from a lack of time to engage in reading activities, given their commitments to household chores and responsibilities. The following transcriptions exemplify the reading difficulty challenges experienced by the participants, particularly concerning the excessive household responsibilities assigned to them:

Participant 4: *Daghan sugu sa balay. Humanun sa ang trabahu ayha magtuun. (There are many chores at home. I have to finish the work before studying.)*

Participant 6: *trabahuun sa balay. (There are many chores at home)*

Participant 11: *Daghan trabahuun sa balay, unahon ang trabahu ayha magbasa. (There are many chores at home; I prioritize the tasks before reading.)*

Participant 13: *Sigi tawagun ug suguun ni mama. mau dili mkapractice ug basa. (My mom keeps calling and instructing me, so I can't practice reading)*

The results from Participants 4, 6, 11, and 13 point to a common problem that the students have: their ability to participate in reading activities is hampered by household responsibilities. There are a lot of chores at home, as mentioned by participants 4, 6 and 11, and they emphasize that these chores must be finished before spending time studying or reading. This implies that taking care of the family comes first and could reduce the amount of time students have to devote to their studies.

Participant 13 highlights how difficult it is to find time for reading practice due to their mother's constant calls and instructions, which adds another level of difficulty to this challenge. The findings collectively point to a significant influence of domestic duties and family obligations on the students' reading practices. This emphasizes the importance of understanding and addressing these external factors when implementing interventions or support mechanisms to enhance the students' reading skills.

Telfer et al. (2014) highlight a potential adverse impact on reading ability linked to frequent participation in housework. Their study suggests a significant association between regular engagement in household chores and potential challenges to reading skills. The findings underscore the importance of understanding the complex interplay between daily activities and cognitive functions. This nuanced understanding is crucial for recognizing factors that may affect reading abilities in individuals regularly involved in housework.

Further research and contextualization of these findings could offer insights into developing strategies that address negative impacts and promote a balanced approach to both daily responsibilities and literacy.

Lacking family support

Another noteworthy theme that emerged from the students' responses is the absence of family support. Below are data points from the investigation that illustrate the lack of family support:

Participant 13: *Sigi kasab an sa balay. (My mom keeps calling and instructing me, so I can't practice reading)*

Participant 17: *Walay gatudlu sa aku ug basa sa balay. (No one teaches me how to read at home.)*

Participant 8: *Tawagun sa maestra unya dili ko katubag, maghilaka daun sa balay. pasagadan rako sa balay. (The teacher will call me, and if I can't answer, I will cry at home. They will just leave me to cry, and no one will help me)*

The statements from the participants' feedback underscore diverse obstacles linked to reading and phonological awareness. Participant 13 highlighted that disruptions caused by their mother impede their reading practice, while Participant 17 conveyed the absence of reading guidance at home. Additionally, Participant 8's response revealed a distressing encounter associated with reading and seeking assistance from family members.

It is evident that external elements, such as interruptions and the lack of reading guidance at home, play a substantial role in limiting individuals' opportunities for reading practice and the cultivation of phonological awareness. Furthermore, the distress conveyed by Participant 8 emphasizes the critical need for well-designed interventions and robust support systems to effectively address reading difficulties and challenges related to phonological awareness.

Moreover, Dudych (2015) emphasizes the pivotal role of robust home support in aiding struggling readers. The research underscores that a strong support system at home, encompassing various forms of assistance and encouragement, significantly contributes to the improvement and success of individuals facing challenges in reading. This includes not only academic guidance but also emotional and motivational reinforcement, creating a comprehensive foundation for the development of struggling readers. The findings underscore the holistic impact of a supportive home environment on the reading outcomes of individuals grappling with difficulties in this skill.

In general, the participants' feedback emphasizes the crucial role of phonological awareness interventions and underscores the necessity of addressing external factors that might impede the development of individuals' reading and phonological awareness. Similarly, Nishikawa (2016) underscores the importance of phonological awareness in reading success and the effectiveness of

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interventions in improving reading skills, particularly for struggling readers. These results highlight the importance of establishing supportive environments and implementing impactful interventions to nurture reading skills and phonological awareness in individuals.

Experiencing bullying

The participants revealed that struggling with reading difficulties exposes them to bullying from other students. The following accounts detail the experiences shared by the participants:

Participant 5: *Ginabully ko kay dili ko kabasa. (I am being bullied because I can't read).*

Participant 7: *Sigi bullyhun kay dili kabasa. (I am consistently bullied because I cannot read).*

Participant 8: *Daghan gabully sa aku tungud kay dili ku kabalu ug basa. (Many people bully me because I don't know how to read).*

Participant 9: *Gasawayun ku sa mga classmates kay ku dili kabasa. (My classmates tease me because I can't read.)*

Together, these participant statements reveal a disturbing pattern of bullying connected to the participants' poor reading skills. Participant 5 reports experiencing explicit bullying as a result of their reading difficulties, while Participant 7 highlights the bullying's persistent nature and links it to their incapacity to read. The statement made by participant 8 sheds light on a larger issue by saying that many people bully them due to their poor reading comprehension. This points to a widespread, beyond-individual encounter social problem associated with literacy.

In a similar vein, Participant 9 highlights classmates making fun of them specifically for their inability to read. While the term "tease" suggests a less overt form of bullying, it underscores the negative social repercussions associated with reading difficulties. These findings align with research by Turunen et al. (2021) and Turunen (2021), emphasizing peer-reported involvement in school bullying among students with reading difficulties. The research underscores that children with reading difficulties are more frequently affected by bullying, whether as victims, bullies, or both, compared to those without reading difficulties.

In summary, the participants' experiences underscore the social impact of struggling with reading skills, involving bullying, consistent teasing, and a broader societal response. Addressing these issues may necessitate not only educational interventions but also increased social awareness and support. In a nutshell, the insights extracted from participants' responses, when analyzed through the lens of phonological awareness and reading interventions, enrich our comprehension of the impact of external factors on individuals' reading habits and fluency. Factors such as household responsibilities, interruptions, lack of family support, and bullying emerge as influential elements shaping the dynamics of reading experiences.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study anchors in the belief that Phonological-based Instruction in Teaching effectively addresses the reading challenges of frustrated high school students. The investigation strengthens

this framework, revealing a robust link between phonological awareness interventions and notable improvements in oral reading and comprehension scores.

Moreover, the study highlights the significant impact of domestic duties and family obligations on students' reading practices. It also underscores the role of external elements like interruptions and lack of home guidance in limiting reading opportunities and phonological awareness development. Also, the research unveils that children with reading difficulties face increased susceptibility to bullying.

The study conclusively affirms the effectiveness of phonological awareness intervention in significantly improving oral reading and comprehension scores, providing empirical support for the principles of Schema Theory. It is imperative to recognize and address the impact of domestic duties and family obligations on students' reading practices when implementing interventions to enhance reading skills. Furthermore, addressing external elements, such as interruptions and the lack of reading guidance at home, is essential to create abundant opportunities for reading practice and the development of phonological awareness, aligning with Schema Theory principles.

In addition, targeted support for children grappling with reading difficulties becomes imperative to mitigate their increased vulnerability to bullying, underscoring the need for tailored interventions in line with Schema Theory. These recommendations underscore the vital importance of persisting with Phonological-based Instruction in Teaching and the necessity for comprehensive support mechanisms to enhance reading skills. This persistence and support are particularly crucial, given the multifaceted nature of factors influencing reading abilities and the validated insights from Schema Theory.

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